

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS
“COMPUTATIONAL PHYLOGENETICS AND THE INTERNAL
STRUCTURE OF PAMA-NYUNGAN”

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1. DATA SOURCES

Sources for the lexical material used are given below, listed by Pama-Nyungan subgroup and language. We are grateful to the authors of unpublished materials who allowed their use for this work, and to the former Aboriginal Studies Electronic Data Archive (aseda.aiatsis.gov.au).¹ The lexical database underlying the cognate codings cannot be published at present because of access restrictions placed on the data. The restrictions were occasionally placed by researchers and Aboriginal community groups, but more often were made by the archives from which data were obtained. Some of these issues are described in Bovern (2012b). Attempts are being made to make at least some of the data freely available to researchers and community groups.

Languages with more than 50% missing data are asterisked. Note that we use the term ‘language’ without reference to language/dialect status. There is no generally accepted term for the unit of analyses we pursue. They are not ‘doculects’, since we use data from more than one source for some languages (though note in the case of some languages that we have taken a ‘doculectal’ approach by including both early sources (e.g. Kamilaroi) and modern sources (Gamilaraay)). They are not ‘dialects’, since some are themselves internally diverse (e.g. Wangkangurru). Note, moreover, that Australianists have been quite inconsistent in the application of terms such as ‘language’ and ‘dialect’ in some areas. The Yolŋu bloc, for example, has been treated as a single language with more than clan lects, though others (e.g. Schultze-Berndt

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¹ASEDA no longer exists as a separate project at the Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies, but portions of the Archive have been folded into the AIATSIS library holdings and are available through mura.aiatsis.gov.au as part of AILEC. This project would have been vastly more time-consuming without the electronic dictionaries in ASEDA; more than 30% of the materials for the Pama-Nyungan lexical database originated as ASEDA holdings and we thank the authors who deposited their work in the archive, along with archival stadd.

2000) recognize up to 10 languages. Dixon (2002:xli) recognizes two languages in the Nyulnyulan family, while Bower (2012a) recognizes 8. Further examples are not difficult to find.

- Arandic
 - Alyawarr : Blackman and Moore (2004)
 - Antekerpenhe : Breen (n.d.a)
 - Western Arrarnta : Roennfeldt (2005)
- Bandjalangic
 - Bandjalang : Crowley (1978), Sharpe (1994, 1997, 2005)
 - Minjungbal : Threlkeld et al. (1892)
 - Nggoi-Mwoi : Hanlon (1925)
 - Yugambah : Sharpe (1994, 1997, 2005)
- Central NSW
 - Gamilaraay : Ash et al. (2003), Giaccon and Program (1999)
 - Kamilaroi : Threlkeld et al. (1892)
 - Ngiyambaa : Donaldson (1980, 1997)
 - Wiradjuri : Grant and Rudder (2001), Hosking and McNicol (1993)
 - Yuwaalaraay : Ash et al. (2003), Giaccon and Program (1999), Williams (1980)
- Durubulic
 - Durubul : Bannister (1975)
 - Yagara : Jefferies (n.d.)
- Kalkatungic
 - Yalarnga : Breen (n.d.g), Breen and Blake (2007)
 - Kalkatungu : Blake (1979, 1998)
- Kanyara-Mantharta
 - Jiwari : Austin (n.d.a)
 - Payungu : Austin (n.d.e), Hale and O’Grady (n.d.)
 - Thalanyji : Austin (n.d.b)
 - Tharrgari : Austin (n.d.c)
 - Warriyangga : Austin (n.d.d)
- Karnic
 - Arabana : Hercus (1994, n.d.a), Schebeck (1999)
 - Diyari : Austin (1981, 1990), Reuther (1883?)
 - *Karuwali : Anonymous (1886b), Austin (1990)
 - Kungadutyi : Schebeck (n.d.b)

- Kungkari : Breen (1990), Holmer (1988)
- Mithaka : Breen (n.d.c)
- Mount Freeling Diyari : Anonymous (1886a)
- Ngamini : Reuther (1883?)
- Nhirrpi : Bower (in preparation)
- *Pirriya : Breen (1990)
- Pitta-Pitta : Blake and Breen (1971)
- Wangkangurru : Reuther (1883?)
- Wangkayutyuru : Blake and Breen (1971)
- Wangkumara₁ : Breen (n.d.e), Robertson (n.d.)
- Wangkumara₂ : McDonald and Wurm (1979)
- Yandruwandha : Breen (2004, 1995)
- Yarluyandi : Austin (1990), Hercus (n.d.b)
- Yawarrawarrka : Austin (1990), Reuther (1883?)
- Kartu
 - Badimaya : Yamaji language centre and Marmion (n.d.a)
 - Malgana : Mackman et al. (2003), Marmion and Yamaji language centre (n.d.)
 - Nhanta : Blevins (2001)
 - Wajarri : Yamaji language centre and Marmion (n.d.b)
- Kulin
 - Mathi-Mathi : Blake (1998), Hercus (1994, 1986b), Wafer and Lissarrague (2008)
 - *Piangil : Macredie (1886)
 - Wathawurrung : Blake (1998), Blake and Reid (1994)
 - Woiwurrung : Blake (1998, n.d.), Blake and Reid (1994)
 - *Colac : Blake (1998)
 - *Gunditjmara : Curr (1886c,d)
 - *Wathi-Wathi : Hercus (1986b)
- Lower Murray
 - *Keramin : Horgen (2004), Wafer and Lissarrague (2008)
 - Ngaiawang : Horgen (2004), Moorhouse (1844, 1846), Wafer and Lissarrague (2008)
 - Ngarrindjeri : Horgen (2004), Taplin (1878)
- Maric
 - *Aminungo : Hodgkinson (1886)

- Bidyara-Gungabula : Breen (1973)
- Biri : Breen (2009), Terrill (1998)
- Dharumbal : Terrill (2002)
- *Gairi : Breen (2009), Terrill (1998)
- Gangulu : Terrill (1998)
- *Gudjal : Santo (n.d.)
- Gunggari : Holmer (1988)
- Gunya : Breen (1981b)
- Margany : Breen (1981b)
- *Wadjabangayi : Tindale (n.d.)
- Warungu : Tsunoda (1972, 1981)
- *Yiningay : Breen (1990)
- *Yirandali : Bennett (1927)
- Marrngu
 - Karajarri : McKelson (n.d.), Sands (1989)
 - KarajarriNW : Nekes and Worms (1953)
 - MangalaMcK : McKelson (n.d.)
 - MangalaNW : Nekes and Worms (1953)
 - Northern Mangarla : O'Grady (n.d.b)
 - Northern Nyangumarta : McKelson (1989)
 - Nyangumarta : McKelson (n.d.), Nekes and Worms (1953), O'Grady (1964)
- Mayi
 - Mayi Kulan : Breen (1981b)
 - Mayi Kutuna : Breen (1981b)
 - Mayi Thakurti : Breen (1981b)
 - Mayi Yapi : Breen (1981b)
 - Ngawun : Breen (1981b)
- Mirniny
 - Mirniny : O'Grady (n.d.a)
 - Ngadjumaya : von Brandenstein (1982)
- Ngayarta
 - Kariyarra : Thieberger et al. (n.d.)
 - Kurrama : Dench (n.d.)
 - Ngarla : Brown and Geytenbeek (n.d.)
 - Ngarluma : Hale (n.d.b)
 - Nyamal : Klokeid (n.d.)

- Panyjima : Dench (1994)
- Yindjibarndi : Anderson et al. (n.d.), Wordick (1982)
- Ngumpin-Yapa
 - Bilinarra : Nordlinger and Jones (n.d.)
 - Gurindji : Patrick McConvell (pc)
 - Jaru : Tsunoda (1981), Tsunoda and Kimberley Language Resource Centre (n.d.)
 - Jaru (McC) : Patrick McConvell (pc)
 - Jiwarliny : Hale (1960)
 - *Malngin : Menning et al. (1981)
 - Mudburra : Breen (n.d.d)
 - Mudburra (McC) : Patrick McConvell (pc)
 - Ngardily : Green (n.d.)
 - Ngarinyman : Jones (n.d.)
 - *Southern Walmajarri : Hudson (n.d.)
 - Walmajarri (Billiluna) : Amery and Hudson (n.d.)
 - Walmajarri (HR) : Hudson (1978), Richards and Hudson (1990)
 - Walmajarri (NW) : Nekes and Worms (1953)
 - Warlmanpa : Nash and Hale (n.d.)
 - Warlpiri : Hale (1995), Nash (1986), Schwarz (1996)
- Nyungar
 - Nyungar : Helms (1896)
 - *Wardandi : Curr (1886b), Hester (1886)
 - Watjuk : Moore (1967)
- Paakantyi
 - Kurnu : Hercus (1986a), Mathews (1902), Trulon (1886)
 - Paakantyi : Hercus (1982, 1986a)
- Paman
 - Aghu-Tharrnggala : Jolly (1989)
 - Djabugay : Robertson (1988)
 - *Flinders Island : Sutton (n.d.)
 - Guugu Yimidhirr : Haviland (1972, 1979)
 - *Kaanju : Hale (n.d.a)
 - Kugu Nganhcara : Johnson and Smith (n.d.)
 - Kuku Yalanji : Patz (2002)
 - *Kuku Yalanji (Curr) : Hughes (1886)

- Kurtjar : Black (n.d.)
- Kuuku-Ya'u : Thompson (n.d.)
- Linnghigh : Hale (1997)
- Mbabaram : Dixon (1991a)
- Mbakwithi : Crowley (1981)
- Pakanh : Hamilton (n.d.)
- Umpila : O'Grady (1967, 1976, 1990)
- Wik-Mungkan : Kilham et al. (1986)
- Yidiny : Dixon (1977, 1991b)
- ThuraYura
 - Adnyamathanha : McEntee and McKenzie (1992)
 - Guyani : Reuther (1883?)
 - Kaurna : Teichelmann and Schürmann (1840)
 - Narrungga : Narrungga Aboriginal Progress Association et al. (2006), Wanganeen and Eira (2006)
 - *Ngadjuri : Simpson and Hercus (2004)
 - Parnkala : Le Souf and Holden (1886), Schürmann et al. (1844/1990)
 - Wirangu : Hercus (1994)
- Waki-Kabi
 - Batyala : Bell (2003)
 - *Dawson River : O'Connor (1886)
 - Duungidjawa : Kite and Wurm (2004)
 - Gooreng-Gooreng : Helon (1994)
- Warluwaric
 - Bularnu : Breen (n.d.b)
 - Wakaya : Breen (1981a)
 - Warluwarra : Breen (n.d.f)
 - Yanyuwa : Bradley (n.d.)
 - Yindjilandji : Osborne (1966)
- Wati
 - Kartujarra : Burbidge and Fuller (n.d.)
 - Kukatja : Valiquette (1993)
 - Martu-Wangka : Burgman et al. (2005), Marsh et al. (1992)
 - Ngaanyatjarra : Glass (2006), Glass and Hackett (2003)
 - Pintupi-Luritja : Hansen and Hansen (1992), Heffernan (2000)

- Pitjantjatjara : Goddard (1992), Goddard and Institute for Aboriginal Development (Alice Springs(1993)
- Warnman : Burbidge and Fuller (n.d.)
- Yulparija : McKelson and McCallum (1988–89)
- Wangkatja : Blyth (1988)
- Yardli
 - Malyangapa : Austin (2002)
- Yolngu
 - Dhangu : Schebeck (n.d.a)
 - Dhay’yi : Wunujmurra (n.d.)
 - Dhuwal : Heath (1980b)
 - Dhuwala : Marika-Munungiritj (n.d.)
 - Djambarrpuyngu : Wilkinson (1991)
 - Djapu : Morphy (1983)
 - Djinang : Waters et al. (1983), Waters and Waters (1980), Waters (1989)
 - Gumatj : Zorc (1986)
 - Gupapuyngu : Christie (n.d.), Lowe (1960)
 - Rirratjingu : Zorc (1986)
 - Ritharrngu : Heath (1980a)
 - Yan-nhangu : Baymarrwaja et al. (2005), James (2003)
- Yota-Yotic
 - Yorta Yorta : Bowe and Morey (1999)
 - *Yabula Yabula : Bowe and Morey (1999)
- Yuin-Kuri
 - Awabakal : Lissarrague (2006), Threlkeld et al. (1892)
 - Birrpaiyi : Lissarrague (2010), Steele (2005)
 - Darkinyung : Jones (2008), Steele (2005)
 - Dharawal : Eades (1976)
 - Dharuk : Dawes (1790), Kohen and Blacktown and District Historical Society (1987), Troy (1994)
 - Dhurga : Eades (1976)
 - Gundungurra : Kohen (1993), Steele (2005)
 - *Iyora : Steele (2005), Troy (1994)
 - Karree : Steele (2005), Threlkeld et al. (1892)
 - Katthang : Enright (1900), Lissarrague (2010), Mathews (1904), Steele (2005)

- Ngarigu : Hercus (1986b)
- Ngunawal : Bannister (1975)
- Isolates and unknown
 - Bunganditj : Blake (2003)
 - Dyrirbal : Dixon (1972)
 - Gumbaynggirr : Eades (1979), Muurrbay Aboriginal Language and Culture Cooperative (2001)
 - *Pallanganmiddang : Blake and Reid (1999)
 - Muruwari : Oates (1988)
 - Mary River and Bunya Bunya Country : Mathew (1886)
 - Warumungu : Disbray and speakers (2005), Simpson and Heath (1982), Simpson (2002)

2. ADDITIONAL NOTES ON CODING

Section 2 of the paper describes the language choices and coding procedures. Here we provide further information about specifics of data choice. Where more than one dialect is represented in a source, and where more than one word is represented in a doculect (or variety), choices must be made about which word to use as representative of the meaning category for that variety. Such choices may in principle lead to biasing of coding if not applied consistently. The first problem is when a source contains material from more than one variety. For example, Ash et al. (2003) contains source materials for three varieties: Gamilaraay, Yuwaalaraay, and Yuwaaliyaay. Where possible, we separated such sources by dialect. This was the case for the sources in Ash et al. (2003), for example. However, not all source materials permitted this. Where possible, we used the word that was represented in the greatest number of sources. Otherwise, we used the first word listed.

To be coded as cognate, words had to be cognate in the list meaning. Thus in some cases the words have additional meanings which are not shared. For example, in many languages, the English meanings ‘stick’ and ‘tree’ are the same word, while in others, those meanings are lexicalized with different words. Note that the number of languages for which detailed information on polysemy is available is small compared to the overall number of languages coded. Note also that every attempt was made in choosing words for the meaning list to minimize the inclusion of words which are frequently polysemous in Australian languages.

Words were treated as cognate if the stems were cognate. Thus in example (2) in the text, Yarluyadi *milki* ‘eye’ is cognate with Yanda *miyil* ‘eye’, even though Yarluyadi

has a stem accretion. Likewise, reflexes of *mara* ‘hand’ and *maraj* ‘hand’ (with stem accretion) also treated as cognate, because they are both reflexes of the same protolexeme, albeit with phonological change in some subgroups. However, in compounded words, both elements of the compound had to be cognate for the form to be considered a ‘match’.

3. ADDITIONAL FIGURES

The figures on the following pages provide further information about the Pama-Nyungan proposal discussed here.

FIGURE 1. Consensus tree showing all languages, relaxed stochastic Dollo model

FIGURE 2. Consensus tree showing all languages, relaxed covarion model

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